

Gender-based Variations in Mental Health and Psychosocial Functioning among Adolescents in Disaster-Prone Regions: A Comparative Study in Kodagu, Karnataka

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Adolescents living in disaster-affected areas are likely to experience psychological and social issues due to the disruption of daily activities, family life, and education. In the context of India, studies on gender-based psychological and social variations in adolescents experiencing repeated natural disasters are scarce. For instance, the context of Kodagu in Karnataka is understudied. This analytical-descriptive study involved 379 school-going adolescents (160 boys, 219 girls) from Kodagu district (disaster-prone areas). The study participants were selected using purposive random sampling from 8th, 9th, and 10th standards. Data collection tools used were structured questionnaires on socio-demographic variables, psychological, social, and emotional aspects. Significant gender-based differences were also established in all domains. Boys had higher levels of anxiety/fear, emotional and social well-being, social participation, environmental values, interpersonal skills, self-image, and social interaction than girls. However, both genders had similar levels of cognitive/academic functioning, emotional sharing, and post-disaster symptoms, which include functional anxiety, intrusion, and avoidance. Statistically significant differences were also evident in fathers' educational attainment and occupation. This highlights the need for gender-sensitive psychosocial interventions for adolescents in disaster-affected regions. Improving school-based mental health, family support, and community resilience-building interventions are necessary for promoting the well-being and resilience of youth in disaster-affected regions.

Keywords: Adolescents, disaster-prone regions, gender differences, mental health, psychosocial functioning

The rise in the number and severity of natural disasters across the globe poses threats to the safety and psychological well-being of the population. Teenagers are at an increased risk of developing psychological issues after experiencing natural disasters because of the vulnerable stage at which they are developing physically, mentally, and socially. The impact of natural disasters may lead to psychological issues such as anxiety, depression, post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), and emotional distress in teenagers (Castaño García et al., 2016; Weems & Scott, 2017). The psychological impact of natural disasters may affect the cognitive ability, emotional well-being, and interpersonal relationships of teenagers (Meltzer et al., 2021).

The psychological and social effects of disaster on adolescents are far-reaching. Adolescents who experience disaster events often experience fear, insecurity, sleep problems, and difficulty

concentrating on their academic work (Newnham et al., 2020). Disasters can also affect the social support structures of the affected individuals, which is important for the well-being of adolescents. Studies have shown that disruptions in community structures, including educational settings, have significant effects on the social participation of adolescents, including their relationships with other people (Pouliot et al., 2021). Family support structures, on the other hand, act as protective factors for the effects of disasters on the psychological well-being of adolescents (Gibbs et al., 2021; Vigil & Geary, 2008).

Gender differences have a significant impact on the mental health of adolescents who experience disaster situations. Research findings have shown that female adolescents experience higher levels of depression, anxiety, and PTSD compared to their male counterparts (Muñoz-Nieves et al., 2025). For instance, gender differences in social roles, responsibilities, and expectations may affect female adolescents in disaster situations (Kimerling et al., 2009). Research findings have also shown that suicidal ideation is higher in female adolescents who experience disaster situations (Rahmani et al., 2023).

Despite the existing studies on the effect of disasters on the mental health of adolescents, there is a need to bridge the existing gap in the study of gender differences in the mental health and psychosocial well-being of adolescents in a particular culture and region. In this regard, India, especially the regions that are often hit by floods, landslides, and other types of natural calamities, presents a unique setting for such studies. The Kodagu district of Karnataka, India, is one of the regions that have experienced a number of natural

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disasters in the recent past, causing disruptions in the lives of numerous families and communities. However, there are few studies that have sought to understand the effect of disaster exposure on the mental health and psychosocial well-being of adolescents in this region. Therefore, the objectives of this study are to compare these aspects among boys and girls and to examine emotional symptoms among adolescents in disaster-prone areas of Kodagu district, Karnataka.

Method

Participants

Purposive sampling is used in this study. A total of 379 school-going adolescents in the 8th, 9th, and 10th standards from various schools in the Kodagu district of Karnataka are selected. Among them, 160 are boys and 219 are girls. Sample size is calculated using Krejcie and Morgan's table (1970) for finding the appropriate size of the sample. This table provides guidelines for calculating the appropriate sample size based on the size of the population.

Research Design

An analytical descriptive design is adopted to investigate the differences in mental health and psychosocial functioning among adolescents in disaster-prone areas.

Measures

The data collection method used was structured questionnaires developed on the basis of published literature on adolescent mental health and exposure to disaster. The structured questionnaires used had five sections that measured different aspects of mental health in adolescents. All items were on a five-point scale.

Socio-Demographic Profile Schedule: A socio-demographic schedule was used to collect information related to age, gender, religion, category, class, type of school, education of parents, and occupation of parents, which helped in understanding the characteristics of the participants' backgrounds and described the sample of the study.

Psychological Aspects Scale: The 21-item psychological aspects items were developed by researcher and it was adopted from published article on psychological sequelae reported in adolescent disaster survivors, including anxiety, fear of disaster, intrusive thoughts, mood swings, social-interpersonal difficulties, impairments in daily activities, sleep problems, low self-esteem, and difficulty concentrating in academic work, as documented by Meltzer-Tackett Du et al. (Du et al., 2023; Meltzer et al., 2021).

Social Aspects: This section consisted of 25 items developed by the researcher to assess various dimensions of social functioning among adolescents. The scale evaluates relationship quality with family, teachers, peers, and neighbours, as well as emotional sharing, participation in school and community activities, and perception of family and community environment. It also taps interpersonal skills such as communication, friendship formation, and caring for others. Respondents rated each item on a five-point Likert-type scale, with response options ranging from Never to Always or Very Bad to Very Good, depending on the item; higher scores indicate better social functioning. These Items were taken from a systematic review on social function assessment tools for children and adolescents (Crowe et al., 2011)

Emotional Aspects: This section consisted of 28 researcher-developed items that assessed various emotional responses among adolescents, such as feeling sad, jealous, irritated, or afraid of the future, difficulty expressing opinions, lack of interest in life, feelings of isolation, and emotional reactions in social interactions. Responses were recorded on a five-point Likert-type scale ranging from Always to Never, with higher scores indicating greater emotional distress. This section aimed to capture how adolescents experience and express emotions in everyday life and social contexts (Martín-Ruiz et al., 2023).

Post-Disaster Emotional Symptoms: This section has 14 items developed by the researcher from published article (Şahi & Okan, 2024) to assess how adolescents feel after experiencing a disaster. It includes feelings such as fear of another disaster, sleep problems, anxiety, nightmares, repeated thoughts about the disaster, insecurity, irritability, dissatisfaction with current life, and thoughts of moving away. Responses are given on a five-point scale from "Always" to "Never." Higher scores indicate more severe emotional problems after the disaster. The purpose of this section is to understand the emotional impact of disasters on adolescents living in disaster-prone areas

Psychological aspects, social aspects, emotional aspects and post disaster emotional aspects questionnaire had developed by researcher and items are adopted by published articles, these questions were face and content validated by the experts

Statistical Analysis

The collected data were coded and prepared for statistical analysis. Descriptive statistics such as means and standard deviations were used to analyze the data. Differences in psychological, social, and emotional aspects of boys and girls were also analyzed using the Mann Whitney U test. Statistical significance of differences in boys and girls was also determined using the 'p' value. This analysis also found differences in the mental health of adolescents in disaster-prone areas.

Table 1 summarises the socio-demographic characteristics of boys (n = 160) and girls (n = 219). The age distribution was comparable between groups (boys: 14 years, 45.6%; 15 years, 33.8%; 16 years, 20.6%; girls: 14 years, 45.7%; 15 years, 36.5%; 16 years, 17.8%). Religious affiliation differed, with most boys identifying as Hindu (53.8%) or Muslim (43.8%), and most girls as Muslim (55.3%) or Hindu (42%). Christians and Jains constituted a small proportion in both groups. Regarding caste, 'Others/Not specified' was reported by 45.6% of boys and 56.6% of girls; the remainder identified as SC, ST, OBC, or GM. The majority of participants were enrolled in 10th standard (boys: 42.5%; girls: 44.3%), with the remainder in 8th or 9th standard. School type distribution was similar (government: boys, 44.4%; girls, 46.6%; private unaided: boys, 32.5%; girls, 32.9%; private aided: boys, 23.1%; girls, 20.5%). Fathers' education was primarily matriculation (boys: 33.1%) or higher primary (boys: 23.1%; girls: 36.5%), while mothers' education was predominantly PUC and above (boys: 31.9%) or high school (boys: 30%; girls: 32%). Fathers were mainly daily wage labourers (boys: 30.6%; girls: 39.3%) or self-employed (boys: 28.1%; girls: 33.3%). Most mothers were housewives (boys: 60.6%; girls: 62.6%). Statistically significant differences were observed in fathers' education ($p = 0.008$) and fathers' occupation ($p = 0.039$), while other variables did not differ significantly.

Table 1
Association between Gender and Socio-Demographic Variables

Variable	Category	Boys (n=160) n (%)	Girls (n=219) n (%)	χ^2	p
Age	14 Years	73 (45.6%)	100 (45.7%)	0.588	0.745
	15 Years	54 (33.8%)	80 (36.5%)		
	16 Years	33 (20.6%)	39 (17.8%)		
Religion	Hindu	86 (53.8%)	92 (42.0%)	7.971	0.093
	Muslim	70 (43.8%)	121 (55.3%)		
	Christian	4 (2.5%)	3 (1.4%)		
	Jain	0 (0.0%)	2 (0.9%)		
Caste Category	Others / Not specified	73 (45.6%)	124 (56.6%)	9.526	0.09
	SC	22 (13.8%)	31 (14.2%)		
	ST	9 (5.6%)	16 (7.3%)		
	OBC	49 (30.6%)	41 (18.7%)		
	GM	7 (4.4%)	6 (2.7%)		
Class	8th Standard	47 (29.4%)	50 (22.8%)	2.291	0.318
	9th Standard	45 (28.1%)	72 (32.9%)		
	10th Standard	68 (42.5%)	97 (44.3%)		
Type of School	Government	71 (44.4%)	102 (46.6%)	3.927	0.14
	Private Aided	34 (21.3%)	30 (13.7%)		
	Private Unaided	55 (34.4%)	87 (39.7%)		
Father's Education	Primary	32 (20.0%)	50 (22.8%)	11.791	0.008
	Higher Primary	37 (23.1%)	80 (36.5%)		
	Matriculation	53 (33.1%)	58 (26.5%)		
	PUC & Above	38 (23.8%)	31 (14.2%)		
Father's Occupation	Daily Wage Labour	49 (30.6%)	86 (39.3%)	8.365	0.039
	Farmer	31 (19.4%)	31 (14.2%)		
	Private Employee	35 (21.9%)	29 (13.2%)		
	Self-Employed	45 (28.1%)	73 (33.3%)		
Mother's Education	Primary	31 (19.4%)	35 (16.0%)	7.653	0.054
	Higher Primary	30 (18.8%)	64 (29.2%)		
	High School	48 (30.0%)	70 (32.0%)		
	PUC & Above	51 (31.9%)	50 (22.8%)		
Mother's Occupation	Working	63 (39.4%)	82 (37.4%)	0.146	0.702
	Housewife	97 (60.6%)	137 (62.6%)		

Note. $p < 0.05$ considered significant

Table 2
Gender-wise Differences in Psychological Aspects among Students

Psychological Aspects	Boys (Mean \pm SD)	Girls (Mean \pm SD)	p
Anxiety & Fear	14.73 \pm 3.12	13.59 \pm 3.45	0.002
Emotional & Social Well-being	11.14 \pm 2.54	10.48 \pm 2.79	0.02
Cognitive & Academic Function	17.51 \pm 4.37	17.64 \pm 4.28	0.825
Physical & Behavioral Symptoms	18.96 \pm 3.73	18.46 \pm 3.63	0.196
Severe Psychological Distress	16.98 \pm 2.94	16.60 \pm 2.81	0.11

Note. $p < 0.05$ considered significant

Table 2 presents gender-wise differences in psychological aspects among students. Boys had higher anxiety and fear scores ($M = 14.73 \pm 3.12$) than girls ($M = 13.59 \pm 3.45, p = 0.002$). Emotional and social well-being was also higher among boys ($M = 11.14 \pm 2.54$) compared to girls ($M = 10.48 \pm 2.79, p = 0.02$). Cognitive and academic function scores were similar for boys ($M = 17.51 \pm 4.37$)

and girls ($M = 17.64 \pm 4.28, p = 0.825$). Physical and behavioral symptoms were slightly higher in boys ($M = 18.96 \pm 3.73$) than girls ($M = 18.46 \pm 3.63, p = 0.196$). Severe psychological distress scores were also higher among boys ($M = 16.98 \pm 2.94$) than girls ($M = 16.60 \pm 2.81, p = 0.11$).

Table 3
Gender-wise Differences in Social Aspects among Students

Social Aspects	Boys (Mean ± SD)	Girls (Mean ± SD)	p
Relationship Quality	16.94 ± 2.29	16.62 ± 2.48	0.205
Emotional Sharing	9.94 ± 3.32	9.98 ± 3.52	0.892
Social Participation	18.27 ± 4.10	16.81 ± 4.43	0.001
Environment & Values	22.87 ± 2.92	21.98 ± 2.91	0.004
Interpersonal Skills	22.47 ± 4.47	20.23 ± 5.27	0.001

Note. $p < 0.05$ considered significant

Table 3 presents gender-based differences in social aspects among students. Boys demonstrated slightly higher relationship quality scores ($M = 16.94 \pm 2.29$) compared to girls ($M = 16.62 \pm 2.48$). Emotional sharing scores were comparable between boys ($M = 9.94 \pm 3.32$) and girls ($M = 9.98 \pm 3.52$). Boys scored higher than girls in social participation ($M = 18.27 \pm 4.10$ vs. $M = 16.81 \pm 4.43$, $p =$

0.001), environment and values ($M = 22.87 \pm 2.92$ vs. $M = 21.98 \pm 2.91$, $p = 0.004$), and interpersonal skills ($M = 22.47 \pm 4.47$ vs. $M = 20.23 \pm 5.27$, $p = 0.001$). Significant differences were observed in social participation, environment and values, and interpersonal skills between boys and girls.

Table 4
Gender-wise Differences in Emotional Aspects and Post-Disaster Symptoms among Students

Emotional Aspects	Boys (Mean ± SD)	Girls (Mean ± SD)	p
Self-Image & Internal Well-being	31.58 ± 5.94	29.11 ± 7.13	0.002
Social Interaction	48.19 ± 8.96	46.12 ± 7.59	0.008
Functional & Anticipation Anxiety	25.54 ± 5.38	25.37 ± 5.29	0.993
Post-Disaster Symptoms	Male (Mean ± SD)	Female (Mean ± SD)	p
Intrusion Symptoms	24.73 ± 6.61	24.90 ± 6.06	0.986
Avoidance & Arousal Symptoms	27.36 ± 5.66	27.16 ± 5.75	0.786

Note. $p < 0.05$ considered significant

Table 4 presents gender-wise differences in emotional aspects and post-disaster symptoms among students. Self-image and internal well-being scores were higher among boys ($M = 31.58 \pm 5.94$) compared to girls ($M = 29.11 \pm 7.13$, $p = 0.002$). Social interaction was also higher among boys ($M = 48.19 \pm 8.96$) than girls ($M = 46.12 \pm 7.59$, $p = 0.008$). Functional and anticipation anxiety scores were almost similar between boys ($M = 25.54 \pm 5.38$) and girls ($M = 25.37 \pm 5.29$, $p = 0.993$). Intrusion symptoms were nearly the same among boys ($M = 24.73 \pm 6.61$) and girls ($M = 24.90 \pm 6.06$, $p = 0.986$). Avoidance and arousal symptoms were also similar between boys ($M = 27.36 \pm 5.66$) and girls ($M = 27.16 \pm 5.75$, $p = 0.786$).

Discussion

Socio-demographic Characteristics Adolescents in Disaster Prone Regions

The study examined the socio-demographic factors of boys and girls in the disaster-prone areas of Kodagu in Karnataka. The boys and girls were similar in age, class of study, and school type. However, the boys and girls were significantly different in the educational and occupational levels of the fathers. The majority of the demographic factors were similar in boys and girls.

The findings of this study are consistent with the studies that were carried out in the context of disasters. The studies indicate that the

youth in the community with different socio-economic and educational backgrounds are prone to psychological and social issues after disasters strike (Kar et al., 2007; Mathew et al., 2021). The studies have emphasized that the socio-economic factors of the youth, such as the educational and professional levels of the fathers, affect the ability of the youth to cope with the disasters that strike the community (Chowhan et al., 2016; Newnham et al., 2022).

However, the significant association between gender and fathers' education and occupation could be related to other socio-economic factors in rural communities, where the occupation and education of people may vary in different communities. The communities in the disaster-prone area may be more prone to economic instability, especially those depending on daily wage labor and other unorganized sources of income, which could influence the psychosocial state of the adolescents indirectly. Similar results have also been found in other studies indicating the role of economic instability in the psychopathology of adolescents (Newnham et al., 2022). Mother's education, mother's occupation, age distribution, and type of school did not indicate significant differences in terms of gender. This indicates that basic educational equality and family life may be similar for boys and girls in the study area. Looking at it from a broader point of view, young people in disaster-prone areas face educational gaps, emotional stress, and psychological problems in life (Mushtaq et al., 2017; Negi et al., 2024).

Psychological, Social, and Emotional Aspects of Adolescents in Disaster-prone Regions

This study also investigated gender-based differences in psychological, social, and emotional factors among adolescents residing in disaster-prone regions. Boys exhibited higher levels of anxiety and fear, as well as greater emotional and social well-being, compared to girls. In the social domain, boys showed significantly higher levels of social participation, environmental values, and interpersonal skills. Emotional indicators, including self-image, internal well-being, and social interaction, were also higher among boys. In contrast, cognitive and academic functioning, relationship quality, emotional sharing, and post-disaster symptoms such as functional anxiety, intrusion, and avoidance did not differ significantly by gender.

These results are partially consistent with previous research in disaster-affected contexts. Studies conducted in India and other disaster-prone regions have found that adolescents frequently experience psychological distress, anxiety, and trauma-related symptoms following disasters (Kar et al., 2007; Mathew et al., 2021). Emotional disturbances, including fear, insecurity, and stress, are commonly reported among adolescents exposed to disasters (Aneelraj et al., 2016). However, several studies have found that girls often exhibit higher levels of depression and trauma-related symptoms compared to boys (Siddik et al., 2024) which contrasts with the pattern observed in the current study. Such higher levels of social participation and social skills in boys may be attributed to socialization differences that are common in many rural communities. For instance, boys tend to be more mobile and have many opportunities for socializing in outdoor environments. This may enhance socialization and social confidence. On the other hand, girls may be subjected to limitations in socialization due to cultural and safety issues. These factors may affect self-perception and emotional expression.

The absence of gender variations in several psychological symptoms that occurred after the disaster indicates that the effects of the natural calamity may be experienced by all adolescents, regardless of gender. Previous studies have indicated that natural disasters affect the daily routines and school activities of adolescents. The effects of the natural calamity also impact the social environment of the adolescents. Consequently, emotional stress and psychological vulnerabilities occur in the lives of adolescents (Chowhan et al., 2016; Tripathi et al., 2026). Social support and community connections are important factors that promote resilience and recovery in the lives of adolescents (Newnham et al., 2020). The psychological needs of the adolescents in the region must be taken into consideration to promote the emotional well-being and psychological resilience of adolescents.

Implications for Social Work Practice

The implications of the findings of the study are immense in the context of social work practice, particularly in disaster-prone areas. Social workers play a crucial role in the psychosocial well-being of adolescents who are exposed to disaster-related psychological distress. School-based interventions, including counselling and life skill development, may be helpful in coping with disaster-related stress among adolescents. Social workers may also engage the adolescents in group activities that improve their social support and social participation skills. At the community level, social workers

may engage with schools, families, and community agencies to develop disaster preparedness interventions among adolescents. Gender-sensitive interventions are also essential in understanding the social and emotional needs of both boys and girls. Family support systems and community awareness about the psychosocial well-being of adolescents are also essential in promoting the psychosocial well-being of adolescents in disaster-prone areas.

Strength, Limitation and Future Research Direction

This study has significant strengths. It fills the information gap on gender differences in mental health and psychosocial well-being of adolescents in disaster-prone regions of India, utilizing a large sample of school-going adolescents and a structured, multidimensional approach to examining psychosocial, emotional, and disaster-related symptoms. This study, however, also has certain limitations. The study's cross-sectional nature and reliance on biased self-report measures are limitations. The study's sample was from a few schools in Kodagu, and future studies need to consider longitudinal designs, larger and more diverse samples, and aspects such as coping, resilience, and family and community support.

Conclusion

This study identified significant gender-based differences in psychological, social, and emotional functioning among adolescents in disaster-prone regions of Kodagu, Karnataka. Boys exhibited higher levels of social participation, interpersonal skills, and specific emotional indicators, whereas several psychological and post-disaster symptoms were comparable between genders. These results indicate that disaster exposure broadly impacts adolescents, but gender-related social and cultural factors influence psychosocial outcomes. Enhancing school-based mental health services, family support systems, and community interventions is crucial for fostering resilience and improving psychosocial well-being among adolescents in disaster-prone areas.

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